

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Spain

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Types of Local Government

The Spanish Constitution assigns public authority to four levels of government: the central state, autonomous communities, provinces and municipalities. Spain consists of 17 autonomous communities, two autonomous cities (Ceuta and Melilla), and two types of local bodies: 50 provinces and 8,131 municipalities.

The Constitution includes two principles regarding local government: the right to 'local autonomy' from all public authorities including the state legislature, and legislative powers over local government given to the central state and autonomous communities. The constitutional recognition of a right to local autonomy (Article 137 of the Constitution [CE]) implies that the municipalities and provinces are not merely internal divisions of the autonomous communities, but part of the state as a whole. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the guarantee of local autonomy 'does not ensure specific contents or spheres of authority established and fixed once and for all, but rather the preservation of an institution in terms that are recognizable for the image that society has of such institution in each time and place' (Ruling of the Constitutional Court [STC] 32/1981). Local autonomy is contrary to any hierarchical position of the local governments under the state or the autonomous communities.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The legal system of local government falls under the concurrent jurisdiction of the state and the autonomous communities. The state has the power to establish the 'basis of the legal system of the public administrations'. On the other hand, the statutes of autonomy confer to the autonomous communities complementary powers over local government. In interpreting the Constitution together with the statutes of autonomy, the Constitutional Court has concluded that the Spanish local system has a 'two-fold nature'. The state is responsible for the 'fundamental' regulations while the autonomous communities are responsible for the 'non-fundamental' or so-called 'development' regulations (STC 214/1989, FJ 4). When regulating the local government system, both state and autonomous communities' laws must respect local autonomy, as directly guaranteed by Article 137 of the Constitution. But the Constitution does not specify what this local autonomy shall consist of, since it limits itself to a vague connection between local autonomy and 'matters of local interest', without specifying

what these are. Consequently, both state and autonomous communities' laws have a wide margin for regulating the functions and organization of local governments.

The current fundamental regulations of the state on local government are primarily found in two Acts repeatedly amended: Law of the Basis of the Local System (LBRL) of 1985, and a Royal Legislative Decree of 2004, which approves the Restated Text of the Local Tax Authorities Act (LHL). This far, the state has interpreted its own 'fundamental' powers broadly, limiting the legislative and executive powers of the autonomous communities. The amendment of several statutes of autonomy since 2006 has not changed this situation.

Generally speaking, Spain's current local government system includes very limited state and autonomous community supervision or control on municipal and provincial activity. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the local autonomy guaranteed by Article 137 excludes these governmental controls to a great extent (STC 4/1981). In the absence of such controls, only courts are ordinarily responsible for oversight of the administrative activity of local councils. The LBRL replaces state and regional controls on local governments with a complex system of intergovernmental relations based on the idea of full respect for the powers of local institutions and the principle of cooperation. Basically, the LBRL establishes legal instruments to prevent conflicts between state and autonomous communities on one hand, and local authorities on the other while obliging local governments to share information with other government levels. To prevent or resolve conflicts of authority, the law promotes the 'free cooperation' of public administrations, either in the form of agreements or by participation in collaborative bodies, and by encouraging local level administrations to participate in the decision-making processes.

On this legal basis, the Spanish local government system has overall functioned satisfactorily since 1985. Local government is thoroughly democratized and has been receptive to new forms of participatory democracy. The elimination of controls from the upper-level territories has resulted in significant improvements to local public services, despite some cases of corruption in urban planning.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

The Spanish local government system is very uniform and symmetrical due to the approaches of both the central state and most autonomous communities: the central state has established a common two-tier system with few variations for all Spain; and the autonomous communities have introduced very few particularities for the local government of their territory.

First, the state maintains a structure of local government that, to a large extent, was defined in 1833. That is, each village, town or city is a municipality. And the whole territory of Spain is divided into 50 provinces which currently (not originally) act as the second level of local government. Every municipality is integrated in a province.

Second, regional particularities within the 17 autonomous communities are scarce. It has been said before that each autonomous community has legislative power to develop the state basic legislation on local government. But since the state basic legislation is in fact very intense and extensive, and imposes a local government scheme made up of municipalities and provinces, the possibilities of innovation for any autonomous community are quite limited. Particular institutions have appeared especially in Catalonia and Aragon, which add a third level of government: the townships (*comarcas*). Also, in the areas of some large cities such as Barcelona, Madrid, Vigo or Valencia there are some metropolitan government structures, normally focused on the management of very specific municipal services. The metropolitan area of Madrid does not have its own government structure because that space is occupied by the regional government (the Autonomous Community of Madrid).

Political and Social Context in Spain

Local politics is largely symmetrical to national and regional ones. National or regional parties also act at the local level. And this limits the effective autonomy of local politicians, even though they are elected locally. Currently, after the municipal elections of May 2019, most municipalities have leftist governments, although many of them are minoritarian. Some very important cities, such as Madrid, Malaga or Zaragoza, have conservative municipal governments.

Provincial governments are indirectly elected, by the councilors of the municipalities in each province. In that indirect election the political parties have great power. In this way, provincial governments normally reproduce municipal political majorities.

Beyond the local level, the general political situation shows common features to many other European countries: strong polarization of politics and absence of clear majorities. This has led to the current – and for the first time since 1978 – coalition government, between the traditional center-left Social Democratic Party (PSOE) and a new radical left-wing party (Unidas Podemos).

The general social and political situation is marked by two circumstances. A national economy that, although formally recovered from the great crisis of 2008, still shows very high unemployment rates (around 15 per cent of the active population), and where income inequalities dramatically increase. The second major social and political concern is the territorial integrity of Spain. Since approximately 2010 a very strong independence movement has emerged in Catalonia, which is one of the richest regions in Spain. This secessionist movement has the support of approximately 50 per cent of the population of the region.

More than 80 per cent of the 8,131 Spanish municipalities are very small having less than 5,000 inhabitants. Given the technical and economic incapacity of these municipalities, in many tasks they are replaced by the 50 provinces, which show a remarkable financial capacity. In some

autonomous communities such as Catalonia or Aragon there are, in addition to the provinces, other intermediate supra-municipal local entities.

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